

HyPlantPro: A Hydrogen Plant Process design framework for optimizing small-to-medium hydrogen plant design specifications

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The transition to green hydrogen production is a cornerstone in global efforts towards decarbonizing industrial sectors and reduce dependency on fossil fuels. As industries seek sustainable energy alternatives, hydrogen production systems powered by renewable energy sources offer a promising solution. However, designing a reliable, standalone green hydrogen production plant for commercial use requires addressing the stochastic nature of renewable energy production. This variability introduces unique challenges, particularly in determining optimal system sizing especially for small-to-medium-scale plants that need to sustain continuous hydrogen output. Without precise design specifications, these systems may suffer from inefficiencies or, conversely, be over-designed, resulting in unnecessary cost and resource allocation.

This paper presents a comprehensive framework designed to calculate the optimal design specifications for a green hydrogen production plant powered by solar energy and supported by a battery storage system. The main design aspects that the framework aims to specify are the capacities of the solar power installation, and the energy and the hydrogen storage. The proposed framework systematically addresses key engineering challenges, including dynamic load management and the need to accommodate renewable energy production intermittency through an integrated energy (batteries) and hydrogen storage solution. The framework also incorporates critical operational constraints, such as the requirement for continuous 24/7 hydrogen supply and maintaining specified hydrogen pressures, which are essential for safe and effective storage design, affecting both pressure systems settings and storage capacity dimensions.

To validate the framework's effectiveness, simulation results are presented, showcasing its ability to provide insight towards the efficient design of a green hydrogen plant. As a case study, the framework has been applied to a pilot plant unit located in Thessaloniki, Greece. This plant will provide make-up hydrogen for the novel TRL6 hydrotreatment unit in the ABATE project, demonstrating the framework's adaptability and relevance to emerging industrial applications. By aligning the plant's design parameters with the fluctuating availability of solar power, this approach ensures consistent hydrogen production while optimizing storage and production capacity and at the same time minimizing the chance on over-designing the system.

The framework introduced in this paper represents a solid methodology for advancing scalable and sustainable hydrogen production systems. Its adaptability to diverse renewable energy production profiles supports the development of green hydrogen plants suited to a variety of grid and off-grid applications, paving the way for broader adoption of clean hydrogen technologies across various sectors.

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